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Daily locomotor activity rhythms of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera: nocturnal or diurnal, and why?

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Abstract: The daily activity patterns of insects are usually based on field observations where they are trapped by the light at night or collected in flight during the daytime. In this study, an actograph was used for quantitative examinations of the daily activity patterns of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. In the actograph, a fine infrared beam (1 mm in diameter) passes the central part of a hyaline vessel, and interruptions of the beam by an insect's movement placed in the vessel are successively pen-recorded on a chart paper sent from the recorder for several days. The obtained actograms suggested that adults of the most species of Neuroptera are nocturnally active and rest in the daytime. However, adults of Raphidioptera and some species of Neuroptera are active in the daytime or at dusk and dawn. Their daily activity patterns are discussed from the perspective of the relationships between their color patterns, palatability, and mimicry. In larvae of Neuroptera, most species of Chrysopidae were diurnally active irrespective of their adult nocturnality. The physiological mechanisms by which individuals shift from diurnal to nocturnal rhythms during developmental stages are still unknown.

Key words: actogram, aposematic mimicry, chemical defense, crepuscular activity, predation avoidance.

INTRODUCTION

Many insects exhibit regular daily cycles by synchronizing their endogenous circadian rhythms with daily changes in the external environment (CORBET 1960; LAZZARI & INSAUSTI 2008). Daily cycles of insect activity can be diurnal, nocturnal, or crepuscular, and one of the evolutionary factors affecting these cycles seems to be predation avoidance (LANGERHANS 2007). Currently, lizards, birds, and bats are the main insect predators, but historically, diurnal lizards and birds appeared first, followed by nocturnal bats (CONNER & CORCORAN 2012). In environments dominated by diurnal lizards and birds, nocturnal insects have an advantage in avoiding predation. Conversely, in environments dominated by nocturnal bats, diurnal insects have an advantage in avoiding predation by them. However, in the present

environments, where these diurnal and nocturnal predators coexist, determining which type of the daily activity pattern is advantageous for insects is a complex ecological problem (SPEAKMAN *et al.* 2000; MALMQVIST *et al.* 2018; BULLINGTON *et al.* 2021).

Daily activity patterns of insects are also related to the evolution of mimicry. Mimicry occurs through interactions between prey and visually foraging predators, such as lizards, birds, and mammals, and is seen in many insects (WICKLER 1968; RUXTON *et al.* 2018). One form of mimicry is camouflage, which makes it difficult to distinguish between itself and the background, thereby avoiding predation. Insects that live in forests and grasslands often have green bodies, the color of living plants, or brown bodies, the color of dead plants. Insects that live on sandy beaches or rocks tend to have gray bodies to make them less noticeable. Another form of mimicry occurs through aposematic coloration of prey. The poisonous (or unpalatable) prey species are often diurnal and have aposematic coloration to enhance prey selection learning for predators. In the case of Müllerian mimicry, cohabiting poisonous species have similar aposematic coloration (MÜLLER 1879) and in Batesian mimicry, the color pattern of non-poisonous species resembles the aposematic coloration of cohabiting poisonous species (BATES 1862).

In this study, we examined the relationships between daily activity patterns and possible aposematic coloration in Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. Raphidioptera includes about 250 extant species of two families and Neuroptera includes about 6600 extant species of 16 families (ENGEL *et al.* 2018; ZHANG *et al.* 2025). The daily activity patterns of insects are usually based on field observations that they are trapped by the light at night or collected in flight in the daytime. On the other hand, research has also been conducted in the laboratory to quantitatively record daily activities. In Neuroptera, DUELLI (1986) recorded the sounds produced at contact of the wings and the 500 mL plastic cup lid when adults of Chrysopidae flew, using a microphone for 24 h at 20°C under natural light. ÁBRAHÁM and coworkers put 10 conspecific individuals of adult Sisyridae, Osmylidae, Coniopterygidae, Mantispidae, Chrysopidae, Hemerobiidae, Myrmeleontidae, and Ascalaphidae into the 300 mL glass vessel (10 sets) and the number of active (antennal movement, walk and flight) individuals were counted at 15-min intervals for 24 h at 25°C under natural light (ÁBRAHÁM 1998; ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006). In the field, the daily activity patterns are monitored by VAS *et al.* (1999), who set the suction trap in the field during March to November and picked up the insects vacuumed by air flow 1000 m³/h at dawn and dusk every day. BELUŠIČ *et al.* (2010) counted the number of adult Ascalaphidae in the field at 15-min intervals for 14 h. These data reveal that most species of Neuroptera are nocturnally active, but some are crepuscular or diurnal. However, their observations are limited to a 24-h cycle, and it is not confirmed whether the observed patterns are repeated daily or not.

Therefore, we used an actograph, which can automatically record the activity of a single insect for long time to compare the daily activity rhythms among a wide range of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. The daily activity patterns were also compared between larval and adult stages. We further investigated whether diurnal species are unpalatable or not in predation experiments using lizards and discussed the possibility of mimicry.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Daily patterns of locomotor activity were examined for field-caught or laboratory-emerged 106 adult individuals of 1 species of Raphidioptera (1 Inocelliidae) and 50 species of Neuroptera (1 Sisyridae, 1 Nevrothidae, 5 Osmylidae, 2 Coniopterygidae, 1 Dilaridae, 1 Berothidae, 3 Mantispidae, 17 Chrysopidae, 5 Hemerobiidae, 10 Myrmeleontidae, and 4 Ascalaphidae) (Table 1). A total of 27 larvae of 1 species of Raphidioptera (1 Inocelliidae)

and 12 species of Neuroptera (7 Chrysopidae and 5 Myrmeleontidae) were also examined for their daily activity patterns (Table 1). However, no adults and larvae were available to record the daily activity patterns of the other families of Raphidioptera (Raphidiidae) and Neuroptera (Rhachiberothidae, Ithonidae, Psychopsidae, Nymphidae and Nemopteridae).

Daily activity patterns were recorded using an actograph hand-made by Masatoshi Nakane. A fine infrared beam (1 mm in diameter) is passed at the central part of a hyaline glass or plastic vessel including an insect (Fig. 1A–F). If the beam is interrupted by the individual, a 1.5-volt battery current flows and is recorded on a chart paper sent out at 10 mm/h from a pen recorder (PR8112; Hioki, Nagano, Japan) (Fig. 1G). The size of the vessels containing one individual varied depending on the size of the individuals, and the following 13 types (Fig. 1 A–F) were used: The Type A (8 mm in diameter, 17 mm in length), Type B1 (16 mm, 30 mm), Type B2 (21 mm, 35 mm), and Type B3 (30 mm, 55 mm); and Type C1 (21 mm in diameter, 15 mm in height), Type C2 (32 mm, 15 mm), Type D (68 mm, 14 mm), Type E1 (58 mm, 37 mm), Type E2 (82 mm, 43 mm), Type F1 (30 mm, 55 mm), Type F2 (45 mm, 42 mm), Type F3 (67 mm, 85 mm), and Type F4 (75 mm, 90 mm). The vessels of Types A and B were plugged with moist tissue paper, and water was added as needed to prevent the plugs from drying out. In the vessels of Types C–E, a wet filter paper was placed at the bottom, and water was added as needed to prevent it from drying out. In the vessels of Type F, the bottom was filled with sand for non-pit-building antlion larvae to hide. In this study, the daily locomotor activity patterns were not observed for pit-building antlion larvae because of frequent interruptions of beams by their sand tossing behavior.

Insects were maintained and their activities were recorded in a temperature-controlled room at 23±2°C. Fluorescent lighting was used for illumination, with a 14-h light and 10-h dark period (lights on at 6:00 and off at 20:00). The illuminance at the position of the vessel containing the insect in the actograph was ca. 400 lux (Range 368–445) which was measured by an illuminance meter (LM-230, AS ONE Cooperation, Osaka). Activity recordings were interrupted by a few minutes' break during which the adult insects were given the fermented milk, CALPIS Water (Asahi Soft Drinks Co., Ltd., Tokyo), to provide potential sustenance and water supply. A small piece of tissue paper soaked with the fermented milk was placed near the insect's mouth using forceps (Fig. 1H, I). In Mantispidae, the field-caught adult or subadult mayflies (Baetidae and small-sized Ephemerellidae) were offered as prey in addition to the fermented milk (Fig. 1I, J). In larvae of Chrysopidae, the field-collected colonies of the aphid *Shivaphis celti* DAS, 1918 were offered as prey (Fig. 1K, L). In larvae of Myrmeleontidae, larvae of the cricket *Acheta domesticus* (LINNAEUS, 1758), the beetle *Tenebrio molitor* LINNAEUS, 1758 (mealworms), or the chironomid *Prosilocerus akamusi* (TOKUNAGA, 1938) were offered as prey. Feeding was usually done once a day. However, to be able to distinguish between activity caused by feeding and the actual daily activity due to the light-dark cycle, feeding was not done regularly every day, but rather at irregular intervals. Furthermore, for species that are tolerant to hunger, feeding was done less frequently to avoid behavioral changes due to feeding.

Palatability assessment

Palatability of 11 species of Neuroptera (1–6 individuals of each species) was assessed using the lizard, *Plestiodon finitimus* OKAMOTO et HIKIDA, 2012. The lizards were captured at Hachioji, Tokyo, and were kept individually in a plastic cage (200 mm × 350 mm, 200 mm in depth) at 23–34°C with natural day length. The bottom of the cage was covered with soil (10 mm thick), and a shelter (100 mm × 80 mm) was placed there to serve as a hiding place. Water was always supplied in a cup (90 mm in diameter, 50 mm in depth).

Two mealworms were fed during the 3-h basking period with artificial light every other day. Feeding experiments were conducted on lizards after more than one week from capturing. First, the feeding willingness of each lizard was checked by giving one mealworm after about 30-min basking, and then one test insect was given. One lizard was used for only one prey. Once used lizards were released to the field capture sites after measuring the snout to vent length (SVL). The mean SVL was 59.2 mm (N=29, SD=5.0).

In this experiment, prey palatability does not refer to the difficulty of capturing the prey or whether or not the lizard has already experienced learning in the wild, but rather focuses on the chemical aspects of the insect, such as whether it emits a repellent odor or contains toxic substances. Therefore, adult Osmylidae and Ascalaphidae were given after cutting the forewings near their bases to prevent them from flying out of the cage, but others were intact. Lizard behavior was recorded with a video camera (12 MPx Camera, Apple Inc., Cupertino, CA, USA) of the Apple iPhone 8 (Fig. 1M) but failed to record in giving *Osmylus hyalinatus* and *Libelloides ramburi*. The observation was terminated if there was no approach to the prey for 20 s. The lizard's behavior was discriminated into seven categorized sequences: no response (O), heading and approaching toward prey (I), licking prey (II), pecking prey with their mouthparts (III), biting prey but immediately releasing it (IV), swallowing prey but regurgitating it until the next morning (V), and complete feeding (VI). If not eaten, the lizard's feeding willingness was checked again by giving one mealworm. The time from heading to biting was measured as the time of decision making to feed from video footage.

RESULTS

Daily activity patterns

Table 1 summarizes the daily activity patterns of adult and larval Raphidioptera and Neuroptera examined in this study. In Inocelliidae, adult *Inocellia japonica* OKAMOTO, 1917 was active mainly during the light period (1 in Fig. 2), but the activity pattern of its larva was unclear (1–2 in Fig. 3). The larvae occasionally moved both in the light and dark periods.

In Sisyridae, adult *Sisyra nikkoana* (NAVÁS, 1910) exhibited unclear daily activity patterns; active both in the light and dark periods (2–5 in Fig. 2). In one species of Nevrothidae and five species of Osmylidae, adults were active in the dark, but *Nipponeurorthus punctatus* (NAKAHARA, 1915) were usually more active in the beginning of the dark and just after the light on (6–18 in Fig. 2).

In Coniopterygidae, adults of two species were usually active during the light to the first half of the dark period (19–20 in Fig. 2).

In Dilaridae, adult *Dilar japonicus* MCLACHLAN, 1883 was active in the dark (21 in Fig. 2), although only one female was examined in a short period.

In Berothidae, adult *Isoscelipteron okamotoi* (NAKAHARA, 1914) was active only during the dark period (22–24 in Fig. 2).

In Mantispidae, the activity patterns of adult *Austroclimaciella quadrituberculata* (WESTWOOD, 1852) and *Mantispilla japonica* (MCLACHLAN, 1875) consisted of the light phase and the dark phase (25–29 in Fig. 2), but those of adult *M. transversa* STITZ, 1913 consisted of mainly the light phase (30–33 in Fig. 2).

Adults of all species of Chrysopidae examined in this study were usually active during the dark period (34–69 in Fig. 2). They often continued walking, rather than flying, in the observation vessels during the dark period. In contrast to adults, larvae were active mostly during the light period and rest during the dark period. However, this tendency was not

always clear, particularly unclear in *Chrysopa pallens* (RAMBUR, 1838) and *Pseudomallada astur* (BANKS, 1937) (3–17 in Fig. 3). These tendencies did not differ between the species with the naked and debris-carrying larvae.

In Hemerobiidae, adults of all examined species walked actively and flew during the dark period as in Chrysopidae (70–81 in Fig. 2).

Adults of all examined species of Myrmeleontidae were apt to fly in the narrow vessels, instead of walking, during the dark period but usually rested under the light (82–95 in Fig. 2). Although only non-pit-building larvae were examined, all of them were rather sedentary in the sand. These larvae moved on and just under the sand surface only for a short time irrespective of the light conditions (18–27 in Fig. 3).

The daily activity patterns differed between the species in Ascalaphidae. Adults of *Ascalohybris subjacens* (WALKER, 1853), *Suhalacsa iriomotensis* SEKIMOTO et YOSHIZAWA, 2007, and *Suphalomitus okinavensis* (OKAMOTO, 1909) tended to move flapping their wings around the time the light was turned on and the time it was turned off, whereas adults of *Libelloides ramburi* (MCLACHLAN, 1875) were active during the light period (96–106 in Fig. 2).

Palatability

The lizards ate all mealworms that were given to them before the experiment to confirm their willingness to eat. When the prey was uneaten, all the lizards ate mealworms after that. Adults of two species of Mantispidae, *Mantispilla japonica* and *M. transversa*, five species of Chrysopidae, *Apochrysa matsumurae* OKAMOTO, 1912, *Chrysopa pallens*, *Chrysoperla nipponensis* (OKAMOTO, 1914), *Italochrysa japonica* (MCLACHLAN, 1875), *Pseudomallada cognatellus* (OKAMOTO, 1914), and one species of Myrmeleontidae, *Myrmeleon trigonois* BAO et WANG, 2006 were all eaten by the lizards (Table 2). In Ascalaphidae, one of six lizards eating adult *Libelloides ramburi* was found to regurgitate it in the next morning and all of three lizards did not ate adult *Ascalohybris subjacens* although bit it (Table 2). In Osmylidae, all three lizards approached the offered adult *Osmylus hyalinatus* MCLACHLAN, 1875 and touched it while sniffing frequently but finally left without biting (Table 2).

The time from heading to biting of the lizard differed between prey species. The lizards took more time to bite *Mantispilla transversa* than *M. japonica*, and *Italochrysa japonica* than other chrysopids (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Nocturnal activity of adults and their predation avoidance

Most species of Neuroptera were nocturnal. Nocturnal activity was reported in other neuropteran species (DUELLI 1986; ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999; VAS *et al.* 1999; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006; OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). If diurnal lizards and birds were present and bats were absent, nocturnal insects could avoid predation (SPEAKMAN *et al.* 2000; MALMQVIST *et al.* 2018). The nocturnal activity is also advantage in escaping from the predation by diurnally active aerial insect predators, such as robber flies, damselflies, and dragonflies (PENNY 1982; CORBET 1999). However, nocturnal, insectivorous bats evolved after the appearance of lizards and birds, and now nocturnal insects are vulnerable to bats at night.

In Chrysopidae, all examined species were nocturnal in our study. Other studies also show most species are nocturnal (DUELLI 1980, 1986; ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999; VAS *et al.* 1999; NIJIMA *et al.* 2002; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006). The adults (both males and females) have paired prothoracic glands used for defense (BLUM *et al.* 1973; GÜSTEN & DETTNER 1991; GÜSTEN 1996; ALDRICH *et al.* 2009; ALDRICH & ZHANG 2016). Some species emit a foul

odor from their prothoracic glands, but even in species that do have prothoracic glands, the odor is often so weak that it is undetectable to humans. In our study, *Italo-chrysa japonica* and *Chrysopa pallens* were the smelly species, whereas *Apochrysa matsumurae*, *Chrysoperla nipponensis*, and *Pseudomallada cognatellus* are less smelly. The lizards ate these species if given, although the time taken from heading to biting *Italo-chrysa japonica* was longer than the other species. Adults of Osmylidae have also paired prothoracic glands (eversible glandular reservoir sacs bearing setae) that protrude chemicals when disturbed (GÜSTEN 1996; DETTNER 2015; ALDRICH and ZHANG 2016; YU *et al.* 2023). Their glands differ from those of Chrysopidae, that open laterally in pleurites via ducts. Adults of *Osmylus hyalinatus* were never bitten by the lizards and thus their chemical defense appears to function as a deterrent to lizard predation (also see YU *et al.* 2023). If the bats scoop up prey with their wings and then bite it, the scent released from the prothoracic glands in response to this stimulation may help it avoid predation. However, the prothoracic glands have not been found in the other families of Neuroptera (GÜSTEN 1996).

Flying insects of several groups detect the approach of echolocating bats and evade them (MILLER & SURLYKKE 2001; CONNER & CORCORAN 2012). In the nocturnal moths, they flee away from the direction of the ultrasonic sounds, fly in complex patterns like zigzags, cease wing beats to dive steeply, or remain motionless in place. These responses to ultrasounds function in predation avoidance from bats (ROEDER 1962). Similar responses to the ultrasounds are reported in nocturnal butterflies (YACK *et al.* 2007), beetles (FORREST *et al.* 1995, YAGER & SPANGLER 1997), crickets (POPOV & SHUVALOV 1977, MASON *et al.* 1998), locusts (DAWSON *et al.* 1997), and mantids (YAGER & MAY 1990). In Neuroptera, *Chrysoperla carnea* (STEPHENS, 1836) of the Chrysopidae folds its wings and dives sharply when the bat approaches emitting low-intensity ultrasonic stimuli and abruptly spreads its wings and halts its dive when encountering high-intensity ultrasonic stimuli immediately before the bat captures prey (MILLER 1975). The similar reactions were reproduced using artificial ultrasonic stimuli (MILLER & OLESEN 1979). *Myrmeleon hyalinus* OLIVIER, 1811 of the Myrmeleontidae also responds to ultrasounds, twisting the abdomen, flicking the wings, pausing in flight, and ceasing flight (HOLDERIED *et al.* 2018). *Myrmeleon hyalinus* is most sensitive to 60–80 kHz as like as the chrysopid *C. carnea*, whereas it is little sensitive at 20–50 kHz that is responded by *C. carnea*. It seems likely that different mechanisms evolved in response to ultrasonic signals among nocturnal Neuroptera although still unexamined in most groups. The nightjars and their allies are also nocturnally active aerial insectivorous birds, but they hunt prey visually (JETZ *et al.* 2003). Insects with ultrasonic hearing capabilities are consumed significantly more often by these birds than bats, consistent with an evolved avoidance of echolocating strategies (BULLINGTON *et al.* 2021). In turn, bats consume a greater proportion of non-eared insects.

Diurnal activity of adults and predation avoidance

In Raphidioptera, the activity pattern of *Inocellia japonica* (Inocelliidae) is diurnal (Table 1). VAS *et al.* (2001) suggests this group diurnal because two species of Inocelliidae and four species of Raphidiidae were collected by Malaise traps and suction traps but not collected by light traps. In Neuropterida and its sister group of Coleoptera, UV-receptors sensitive to ultraviolet (~350 nm) were lost in most species but appear to have been reacquired in diurnal species (SHARKEY *et al.* 2017). The UV-receptor is found in the species of Raphidiidae, *Xanthostigma xanthostigma* (SCHUMMEL, 1832), (SHARKEY *et al.* 2017), suggesting its diurnal activity. However, adults are known to be light trapped occasionally (OSWALD

& MACHADO 2018). This is probably because their activities sometimes continue at the beginning of darkness (1 of Fig. 2). Information on the predation avoidance by Raphidioptera is unavailable.

In Neuroptera, some species are diurnal (DUELLI 1986; ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999; VAS *et al.* 1999; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006; OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). Although not based on quantitative data, adults of Myrmeleontidae, *Palpares libelluloides* (LINNAEUS, 1764) and *P. turcicus* KOÇAK, 1976, are mostly diurnal, but a few adults are active and caught around sunset (KOVANCI & KOVANCI 2015; KERIMOVA *et al.* 2021). In our study, the diurnal patterns occurred only in Mantispidae and Ascalaphidae.

In Mantispidae, *Mantispilla transversa* was likely to be diurnal, but *Austroclimaciella quadrituberculata* and *Mantispilla japonica* included both diurnal and nocturnal activity phases within the same individuals. Their body and wing colors are apparently conspicuous and resemble polistine wasps (Fig. II, J, M). Adults of most species of Mantispidae resemble wasps of the families Vespidae, Eumenidae and Sphecidae in their body size and coloration and they may be escaped from predators that learn the wasps equipped with a sting (OPLER 1981; REDBORG 1998; SNYMAN *et al.* 2020), although adults of *Allomantispia*, *Plega*, *Gerstaeckerella*, and *Theristria* have a kind of black or brown camouflage-like marking patterns on body and wings to conceal themselves (LI *et al.* 2020; ARDILA-CAMACHO *et al.* 2024). Previous reports of their daily activity patterns have been vague; nocturnal, diurnal, or active both in the daytime and at night (REDBORG 1998; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006; KRAL 2013; SNYMAN *et al.* 2020). Adults of some Mantispidae species are known to eat pollen and nectar on flowers and prey on other insects (OPLER 1981; BOYDEN 1983). Our study demonstrated that individuals involve two different phases of daily rhythms, diurnal and nocturnal, simultaneously, although the diurnal rhythm dominates in *Mantispilla transversa*. Such daily rhythms explain well the inconsistent results known so far. Although the lizard took slightly more time to bite *Mantispilla transversa* than *M. japonica*, they finally ate both. Therefore, these mantispids are considered palatable for predators and have Batesian mimicry to the wasps.

In Ascalaphidae, *Libelloides ramburi* was diurnal. *Libelloides macaronius* (SCOPOLI, 1763) is also the diurnal species (ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006; BELUŠIČ *et al.* 2010). Unusually within Neuroptera, this species has the UV-receptor and its sensitivity shift to the UV range may be advantage in detecting small insect prey as contrasting spots against clear and cloudy skies in the daytime (BELUŠIČ *et al.* 2013; van der KOOI *et al.* 2021). Adults of *Libelloides* species have conspicuously yellow patterned wings (Fig. 10). Development of aposematic coloration of insects is promoted as a set of conspicuous color, toxicity/unpalatability, and diurnal activity via learning of the visually foraging predators, such as insectivorous lizards, birds, and mammals (STEVENS & RUXTON 2012). However, *Libelloides ramburi* were unlikely to be unpalatable because the lizards ate it, excluding one regurgitation case after eating. This species lives in grasslands and bushes but is difficult to find it with the human eye among brown dead leaves or branches (KARUBE & KAGA 2022). Therefore, such yellowish markings are suggested to be not aposematic but disruptive coloration which is a form of camouflage that works by breaking up their outlines.

In the families of Neuroptera other than Mantispidae and Ascalaphidae, studies on predation avoidance are few and fragmented. In Chrysopidae, the diurnal activity is reported in *Hypochrysodes elegans* (BURMEISTER, 1839) (DUELLI 1986) and *Chrysopa dorsalis* (BURMEISTER, 1839) (ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999). In *Chrysopa perla* (LINNAEUS, 1758) and *Chrysopa dorsalis*, their activity patterns are not nocturnal but unclear (DUELLI 1986).

However, these chrysopids are green colored and cryptic to leaves. Among Chrysopidae, *Italochrysa japonica* has apparently aposematic coloration, pale reddish color on the dorsal parts of the head and thorax and a white and black bands on the abdomen (Fig. 1H). However, they were nocturnally active and eaten by the lizards, suggesting their color patterns are not aposematic but cryptic or disruptive coloration in their grassland habitats. In Sisyridae, the daily activity patterns of *Sisyra nikkoana* was unclear, moving occasionally both in the daytime and at night (also see SAITO *et al.* 2024). Such unclear patterns are also known in *Sisyra fuscata* (FABRICIUS, 1793) and *Sisyra terminalis* CURTIS, 1854 (ÁBRAHÁM 1998; ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999). The activity patterns of Coniopterygidae, *Coniopteryx abdominalis* OKAMOTO, 1905 and *Semidalis aleyrodiformis* (STEPHENS, 1836) were also unclear and active both in the daytime and at night. Most species of coniopterygids are active usually at night but some often active even in the daytime (ÁBRAHÁM & VAS 1999; VAS *et al.* 1999; ÁBRAHÁM & MÉSZÁROS 2006). Most parts of the body and wings of mature adult Coniopterygidae are usually covered with a superficial coating of pale waxy particles (ZIMMERMANN *et al.* 2009; DETTNER 2015; LI *et al.* 2023). However, the effect such wax-covering to avoid predation are still unexamined.

Crepuscular activity of adults and predation avoidance

Adults of a few species of Neuroptera are treated as crepuscular (DUELLI 1986; OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). *Mallada basalis* (WALKER, 1853) of Chrysopidae is crepuscular (DUELLI 1986) and the feeding activity of Ascalaphidae is confined to dusk and perhaps dawn (PENNY 1982). In our study, the crepuscular patterns occurred only in *Ascalohybris subjacens*, *Suhpalacsa iriomotensis*, and *Suphalomitus okinavensis* of Ascalaphidae. In Neuroptera, some individuals of *Nipponeurorthus punctatus* were active for a while at night and at dawn, but it is unclear whether this corresponds to the crepuscular pattern, and further investigation is required.

Most birds are active diurnally and visually hunt aerial insects. The feeding efficiency of birds is constrained by declining visual capacity at dusk, while the feeding activity of echolocating bats is constrained by predation pressure from raptorial birds in bright light (SPEAKMAN *et al.* 2000; MALMQVIST *et al.* 2018). Bats that feed on crepuscular insects typically emerge from their roost and start to feed while the peak activity of insects is already declining (RYDELL *et al.* 1996) and there is 37 min between the insect and bat activity peaks (MALMQVIST *et al.* 2018). Therefore, crepuscular insects allocate the flight activity to dusk and dawn, when predation pressure may be relatively low owing to the constraints acting on diurnal birds and nocturnal bats (MALMQVIST *et al.* 2018). The nocturnal birds, nightjars, hunt flying insects mostly in dusk and dawn (JETZ *et al.* 2003). The effects of their feeding pressure on the activity of crepuscular insects are still unclear. On the other hand, aerial insect predators such as some dragonflies (Odonata) and Ascalaphidae fly actively at dusk and dawn, allowing them to efficiently prey on small insects that swarm at that time (PENNY 1982; CORBET 1999). These two advantages in escaping predation and feeding prey are not mutually exclusive for crepuscular predacious insects.

However, crepuscular insects are not completely protected from bird predation, and so they are expected to develop aposematic coloration in response to birds. In palatability tests, adults of *Ascalohybris subjacens* were not eaten by the lizards, suggesting their unpalatability. This species emits odors and smells as known in some other species of Ascalaphidae (MARQUEZ-LÓPEZ *et al.* 2024). Therefore, their yellow-lined bodies (Fig. 1N) may function as aposematic coloration.

Unexamined neuropteran families

In this study, the daily activity patterns of Rhachiberothidae, Ithonidae, Psychopsidae, Nymphidae, and Nemopteridae were not examined. Although their activity patterns are suggested by the fragmental field observations, the future comparative studies will be needed based on the quantitative data on their activities. Rhachiberothidae includes four extant genera, *Rhachiella*, *Rhachiberotha*, *Hoelzeliella* and *Mucroberotha* (LI *et al.* 2025) or also includes the Symphrasinae genera *Anchieta*, *Plega* and *Trichoscelia* (ARDILA-CAMACHO *et al.* 2024). In the latter case, adults of these three genera are mostly collected at night. Adults of *Plega* have a kind of black or brown camouflage-like marking patterns on body and wings, as in the genera *Allomantispa*, *Gerstaeckerella* and *Theristria* of Mantispidae, which conceal themselves when they perch on trunks or branches bearing lichen or moss (LI *et al.* 2020; ARDILA-CAMACHO *et al.* 2024). In Ithonidae, adults of *Rapisma* are nocturnally active and quietly stay on trees during the daytime (BARNARD 1981) and adults of *Adamsiana* are also nocturnal; males are short-distance flyers from tree to tree at night, whereas wingless females prefer to stay close to the ground (ARDILA-CAMACHO *et al.* 2020). Adults of Psychopsidae are thought to be nocturnal, although the specimens of *Zygophlebius pseudosilvelra* OSWALD, 1994 are collected when flying in the daytime (OSWALD 1994; OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). Adults of Nymphidae are usually captured at lights and probably nocturnal (NEW 2003; OSWALD & MACHADO 2018).

Nemopteridae includes two subfamilies, Crocinae and Nemopterinae. Adults of Crocinae are generally smaller with narrow, threadlike hind wings. They are largely nocturnal or crepuscular and live in arid zones (ENGEL *et al.* 2018). In this subfamily, the species of *Croce* and *Dielocroce* fly exclusively at night, and there are only occasional specimens found during daytime hours in places where they are found in masses at night. The species of *Lertha* have also nocturnal activity, but they are often found sitting on flowers, feeding on nectar in the daytime, especially in the morning hours (DOBOSZ & ÁBRAHÁM 2009). Adult *Lertha sofiae* MONSERRAT, 1988 fly actively only for one hour just after sunset. This species is not observed flying in the daytime and not collected by light trapping at night (MONSERRAT 1996). In Nemopterinae, *Nemoptera* has colored wings, their hind wings apically dilated, and fly in the daytime (DOBOSZ & ÁBRAHÁM 2009; ENGEL *et al.* 2018). Adults of *Nemoptera bipennis* (ILLIGER, 1812) fly for several hours in the daytime (MONSERRAT 1996; ZHENG & LIU 202). Adults of *Nemoptera* and *Sinonemoptera* visit flowers and feed on pollen and nectar by their elongated heads and modified non-biting mouthparts (KRENN *et al.* 2008). However, adults of *Sinonemoptera* are active at night when the river valleys are relatively not windy and the diurnal windy, dry, and hot river valley areas may limit their daytime activity (ZHENG & LIU 2025). Adults of African genera of Nemopterinae, *Nemopterella*, *Nemia*, *Semirhynchia* and *Nemeura*, are also nocturnally active (SOLE *et al.* 2013).

Daily activity patterns of larvae

The larvae of Raphidioptera are usually hidden under the tree barks and eat small arthropods (OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). The daily activity patterns of larval Raphidioptera were unclear, although based on the observation of only two individuals. The larva occasionally moved both in the daytime and at night (1–2 in Fig. 3, Table 1).

In Neuroptera, the lifestyles of larvae are diverse, including parasitic and free-living species, and their habitats range from aquatic to soil and on plants (OSWALD & MACHADO 2018). No research has been conducted on the daily activity patterns of these larvae. In this study, actograms were obtained for several free-living neuropteran larvae of Myrmeleontidae and Chrysopidae (3–27 in Fig. 3, Table 1).

Larvae of Myrmeleontidae are usually ambush predators in sands or fine soils. All examined species of non-pit-building antlions were mostly stationary and occasionally moved on and near the surface of sands, but their daily activity patterns were unclear. The antlion larvae migrate deep to sands in the daytime and close to shallow at night both in pit-building and non-pit-building species (van ZYL *et al.* 1996). However, this daily pattern depends on prevailing environmental conditions to avoid higher sand temperatures in the daytime.

Larvae of Chrysopidae are separated into the two types, naked larvae and debris-carrying larvae (TAUBER *et al.* 2014). The debris carried by the latter larvae has defensive function against their enemies by decreasing the contact, attack, and/or capture rates by the predacious larval ladybirds (NAKAHIRA & ARAKAWA 2006) and ants (HAYASHI & NOMURA 2011; HAYASHI *et al.* 2014, 2016). Some species of larvae of both types can escape from predation by smearing anal fluid onto ants and other predators (LAMUNYON & ADAMS 1987; ALDRICH & ZHANG 2016). Irrespective of these two types, larvae of most species usually exhibited the diurnal activity rhythms, although there was a considerable variation among individuals, particularly in debris-carrying *Pseudomallada astur* and naked *Chrysopa pallens*. In contrast, adults were nocturnally active. No physiological research has been done to date on the transition of daily activity patterns according to the developmental stage of insects. This will be an important challenge for the future. Moreover, we need more information of daily activity patterns for other groups of Neuroptera for comparisons between larval and adult stages.

The endogenous factors, such as age, development, and degree of starvation, and the exogenous factors, such as temperature, humidity, food availability, hiding places, and existence of predators, may affect individual daily activity patterns. In our study, the temperature and humidity were controlled not to fluctuate but the other factors were not controlled. These limitations of this study need to be clarified in the future based on the experiments using a larger number of individuals of respective species.

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REFERENCES

- ÁBRAHÁM L. 1998. A study on the Hungarian freshwater osmylid and sponge-flies fauna (Neuroptera: Osmylidae, Sisyridae). *Somogyi Múzeumok Közleményei* 13: 263–273.
- ÁBRAHÁM L., MÉSZÁROS Z. 2006. Further studies on the daily activity pattern of Neuroptera with some remarks on the diurnal activities. *Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica* 41: 275–286.
- ÁBRAHÁM L., VAS J. 1999. Preliminary report on study of the daily activity pattern of Neuroptera in Hungary. *Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica* 34: 153–164.
- ALDRICH J.R., LE T.C., ZHANG Q.-H., TORRES J., WINTERTON S.L., HAN B., MILLER G.L., CHAUHAN K.R. 2009. Prothoracic gland semiochemicals of green lacewings. *Journal of Chemical Ecology* 35: 1181–1187.
- ALDRICH J.R., ZHANG Q.H. 2016. Chemical ecology of Neuroptera. *Annual Review of Entomology* 61: 197–218.
- ARDILA-CAMACHO A., CASTILLO-ARGAËZ R., MARTÍNEZ J.I. 2020. A new species of moth lacewing from the Mesoamerican genus *Adamsiana* PENNY 1996 (Neuroptera: Ithonidae). *Neotropical Entomology* 49: 435–444.

- ARDILA-CAMACHO A., MACHADO R.J.P., OHL M., CONTRERAS-RAMOS A. 2024. A camouflaged diversity: taxonomic revision of the thorny lacewing subfamily Symphrasinae (Neuroptera, Rhachiberothidae). *ZooKeys* 1199: 1.
- BARNARD P.C. 1981. The Rapismatidae (Neuroptera): montane lacewings of the oriental region. *Systematic Entomology* 6: 121–136.
- BATES H.W. 1862. XXXII. Contributions to an Insect Fauna of the Amazon Valley. Lepidoptera: Heliconidæ. Transactions of the Linnean Society of London 23: 495–566.
- BELUŠIČ G., PIRIH P., STAVENGA D.G. 2013. A cute and highly contrast-sensitive superposition eye – the diurnal owlfly *Libelloides macaronius*. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 216: 2081–2088.
- BELUŠIČ G., PIRIH P., ZUPANČIČ G., STUŠEK P., DRAŠLAR K. 2010. The visual ecology of the owlfly (*Libelloides macaronius*), pp. 89–96. In: DEVETAK, D., LIPOVŠEK S., ARNETT A.E. (Eds), *Proceedings of the Tenth International Symposium on Neuropterology*, Piran, Slovenia, 2008. Maribor, Slovenia.
- BLUM M.S., WALLACE J.B., FALES H.M. 1973. Skatole and tridecene: identification and possible role in a chrysopid secretion. *Insect Biochemistry* 3:353–357.
- BOYDEN T.C. 1983. Mimicry, predation and potential pollination by the mantispid, *Climaciella brunnea* var. *instabilis* (SAY) (Mantispidae: Neuroptera). *Journal of the New York Entomological Society* 91: 508–511.
- BULLINGTON L.S., SEIDENSTICKER M.T., SCHWAB N., RAMSEY P.W., STONE K. 2021. Do the evolutionary interactions between moths and bats promote niche partitioning between bats and birds? *Ecology and Evolution* 11: 17160–17178.
- CONNER W.E., CORCORAN A.J. 2012. Sound strategies: the 65-million-year-old battle between bats and insects. *Annual Review of Entomology* 57: 21–39.
- CORBET P.G. 1960. Patterns of circadian rhythms in insects. *Cold Spring Harbor Symposia on Quantitative Biology* 25: 357–360.
- CORBET P.S. 1999. Dragonflies: Behaviour and Ecology of Odonata. Cornell University Press, Ithaca, NY: XXXII + 1–829.
- DAWSON J.W., DAWSON-SCULLY K., ROBERT D., ROBERTSON R.M. 1997. Forewing asymmetries during auditory avoidance in flying locusts. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 200: 2323–2335.
- DETTNER K. 2015. Toxins, defensive compounds and drugs from insects, pp. 39–93, In: HOFFMANN K.H. (Ed.), *Insect Molecular Biology and Ecology*. CRC, Boca Raton, FL.
- DOBOSZ R., ÁBRAHÁM L. 2009. Contribution to the knowledge of the Turkish tail-wings (Neuroptera: Nemopteridae). *Natura Somogyiensis* 15: 113–126.
- DUELLI P. 1986. Flight activity patterns in lacewings (Planipennia: Chrysopidae), pp. 165–170, In: GEPP J., ASPÖCK H., HÖLZEL H. (Eds.), *Recent Research in Neuropterology. Proceedings of the 2nd International Symposium on Neuropterology 1984*, Hamburg, Germany; held in association with the XVII International Congress of Entomology. Privately printed, Graz, Austria.
- ENGEL M.S., WINTERTON S.L., BREITKREUZ L.C. 2018. Phylogeny and evolution of Neuropterida: where have wings of lace taken us? *Annual Review of Entomology* 63: 531–551.
- FORREST T.G., FARRIS H.E., HOY R.R. 1995. Ultrasound acoustic startle response in scarab beetles. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 198: 2593–2598.
- GÜSTEN R. 1996. A review of epidermal glands in the order Neuroptera (Insecta), pp. 129–146, In: CANARD M., ASPÖCK H., MANSELL MW (Eds.), *Pure and applied research in Neuropterology. Proceedings of the Fifth International Symposium on Neuropterology*, 1994, Cairo, Egypt. Toulouse, France.
- GÜSTEN R., DETTNER K. 1991. The prothoracic gland of the Chrysopidae (Neuropteroidea: Planipennia), pp. 60–65, In: ZOMBORI L. PEREGOVITS L (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Fourth European Congress of Entomology and the XIII Internationale Symposium für die Entomofaunistik Mitteleuropas*, Gödöllő, Hungary. Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.
- HAYASHI M., CHOH Y., NAKAMUTA K., NOMURA M. 2014. Do aphid carcasses on the backs of larvae of green lacewing work as chemical mimicry against aphid-tending ants? *Journal of Chemical Ecology* 40: 569–576.
- HAYASHI M., NOMURA M. 2011. Larvae of the green lacewing *Mallada desjardinsi* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) protect themselves against aphid-tending ants by carrying dead aphids on their backs. *Applied Entomology and Zoology* 46: 407–413.
- HAYASHI M., NOMURA M., NAKAMUTA K. 2016. Efficacy of chemical mimicry by aphid predators depends on aphid-learning by ants. *Journal of Chemical Ecology* 42: 236–239.
- HOLDERIED M.W., THOMAS L.A., KORINE C. 2018. Ultrasound avoidance by flying antlions (Myrmeleontidae). *Journal of Experimental Biology* 221: jeb189308.
- JETZ W., STEFFEN J., LINSENMAIR K.E. 2003. Effects of light and prey availability on nocturnal, lunar and seasonal activity of tropical nightjars. *Oikos*: 627–639.
- KARUBE H., KAGA R. 2022. Ecological knowledge of endangered species *Libelloides ramburi* (M'LACHLAN, 1875) in Kanagawa Prefecture, Japan. *Bulletin of the Kanagawa Prefectural Museum (Natural Science)* 51: 73–80. [in Japanese]
- KERIMOVA I.G., SNEGOVAYA N., KRIVOKHATSKY V.A. 2021. Cohabitation of ant lions *Palpares libelluloides* (LINNAEUS, 1764) and *P. turcicus* KOČAK, 1976 (Neuroptera, Myrmeleontidae). *Journal of the Entomological Research Society* 23: 179–186.

- KOVANCI O.B., KOVANCI B. 2015. Contribution to the knowledge of Mantispodea, Osmyoidea, and Myrmeleontoidea with new records for the Neuroptera fauna of northwestern Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Zoology* 39: 110–118.
- KRAL K. 2013. Vision in the mantispid: a sit-and-wait and stalking predatory insect. *Physiological Entomology* 38: 1–12.
- KRENN H.W., GEREKEN-KRENN B.A., STEINWENDER B.M., POPOV A. 2008. Flower visiting Neuroptera: mouthparts and feeding behaviour of *Nemoptera sinuata* (Nemopteridae). *European Journal of Entomology* 105: 267–277.
- LAMUNYON C.W. ADAMS P.A. 1987. Use and effect of an anal defensive secretion in larval Chrysopidae (Neuroptera). *Annals of the Entomological Society of America* 80: 804–808.
- LANGERHANS R.B. 2007. Evolutionary consequences of predation: avoidance, escape, reproduction, and diversification, pp. 177–220. In: ELEWA A.M.T. (Ed.), *Predation in Organisms: A Distinct Phenomenon*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- LAZZARI C.R., INSAUSTI T.C. 2008. Circadian rhythms in insects, pp. 2–18. In: FANJUL-MOLES M.L., AGUILAR-ROBLERO R. (Eds), *Comparative Aspects of Circadian Rhythms*, Vol. 37. Transworld Research Network, Kerala, India.
- LI H., ZHUO D., WANG B., NAKAMINE H., YAMAMOTO S., ZHANG W., JEPSON J.E., OHL M., ASPÖCK U., ASPÖCK H., NYUNT T.T., ENGEL M.S., BENTON M.J., DONOGHUE P., LIU X. 2025. A double-edged sword: Evolutionary novelty along deep-time diversity oscillation in an iconic group of predatory insects (Neuroptera: Mantispodea). *Systematic Biology* 74: 395–420.
- LI H., WU C., OHL M., LIU X. 2020. A new sexually dimorphic mantidfly species of *Allomantispa* Liu *et al.*, 2015 from China (Neuroptera: Mantispidae). *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology* 23: 988–1002.
- LI M., OSWALD J.D., LIU X. 2023. Comparative morphology of wax gland heads in adult dustywings (Insecta: Neuroptera: Coniopterygidae). *Insecta* 14: 650.
- MALMQVIST E., JANSSON S., ZHU S., LI W., SVANBERG K., SVANBERG S., RYDELL J., SONG Z., BOOD J., BRYDEGAARD M., ÅKESSON S. 2018. The bat–bird–bug battle: Daily flight activity of insects and their predators over a rice field revealed by high-resolution scheidpflug lidar. *Royal Society Open Science* 5: 172303.
- MARQUEZ-LÓPEZ Y., MARTINS C.C., GUEVARA-CHUMACERO L.M., RAMÍREZ-PONCE A., CONTRERAS-RAMOS A. 2024. Comparative morphology of male genitalia in antlions (Insecta, Neuroptera, Myrmeleontidae), with emphasis on owlflies (Ascalaphinae) and a possible structural evolutionary scenario. *Journal of Morphology* 285: e21701.
- MASON A.C., FORREST T.G., HOY R.R. 1998. Hearing in mole crickets (Orthoptera: Gryllotalpidae) at sonic and ultrasonic frequencies. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 201: 1967–1979.
- MILLER L.A. 1975. The behaviour of flying green lacewings, *Chrysopa carnea*, in the presence of ultrasound. *Journal of Insect Physiology* 21: 205–219.
- MILLER L.A., OLESEN J. 1979. Avoidance behavior in green lacewings: I. Behavior of free flying green lacewings to hunting bats and ultrasound. *Journal of Comparative Physiology* 131: 113–120.
- MILLER L.A., SURLYKKE A. 2001. How some insects detect and avoid being eaten by bats: tactics and countertactics of prey and predator: evolutionarily speaking, insects have responded to selective pressure from bats with new evasive mechanisms, and these very responses in turn put pressure on bats to “improve” their tactics. *Bioscience* 51: 570–581.
- MONSERRAT V.J. 1996. Larval stages of European Nemopterinae, with systematic considerations on the family Nemopteridae (Insecta, Neuroptera). *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift* 43: 99–121.
- MÜLLER F. 1879. Ituna and Thyridia; a remarkable case of mimicry in butterflies (transl. by Meldola, R. from the original German article in 1879, *Kosmos* 5: 100–108). *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London* 1879: 20–29.
- NAKAHIRA K., ARAKAWA R. 2006. Defensive functions of the trash-package of a green lacewing, *Mallada desjardinsi* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae), against a ladybird, *Harmonia axyridis* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). *Applied Entomology and Zoology* 41: 111–115.
- NEW T.R. 2003. *The Neuroptera of Malesia*. Brill, Leiden: 1–204.
- NIJIMA K., YOSHIDA T., AKIMOTO T. 2002. Egg collection and cold storage of adults in several Japanese chrysopids as biological control agents for mass rearing. *Bulletin of the Faculty of Agriculture, Tamagawa University* 42: 15–29. [in Japanese]
- OPLER P.A. 1981. Polymorphic mimicry of polistine wasps by a neotropical neuropteran. *Biotropica* 13: 165–176.
- OSWALD J.D. 1994. Revision of the African silky lacewing genus *Zygophlebius* NAVÁS (Neuroptera: Psychopsidae). *African Entomology* 2: 83–96.
- OSWALD J.D., MACHADO R.J.P. 2018. Biodiversity of the Neuropterida (Insecta: Neuroptera, Megaloptera, and Raphidioptera), pp. 627–671. In: FOOTITT R.G., ADLER P.H. (Eds), *Insect Biodiversity: Science and Society*, Vol. II. John Wiley & Sons Ltd., Hoboken, NJ, USA.
- PENNY N.D. 1982. Review of the generic level classification of the New World Ascalaphidae (Neuroptera). *Acta Amazonica* 11: 391–406.
- POPOV A.V., SHUVALOV V.F. 1977. Phonotactic behavior of crickets. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A: Sensory, Neural, and Behavioral Physiology* 119: 111–126.
- REDBORG K.E. 1998. Biology of the Mantispidae. *Annual Review of Entomology* 43: 175–194.

- ROEDER K. 1962. The behaviour of free flying moths in the presence of artificial ultrasonic pulses. *Animal Behaviour* 10: 300–304.
- RUXTON G.D., ALLEN W.L., SHERRATT T.N., SPEED M.P. 2018. Avoiding attack: the evolutionary ecology of crypsis, aposematism, and mimicry. Second edition. Oxford University Press, Oxford: 1–278.
- RYDELL J., ENTWISTLE A., RACEY P. A. 1996. Timing of foraging flights of three species of bats in relation to insect activity and predation risk. *Oikos* 76: 243–252.
- SAITO K., HAYASHI F., SUGAWARA H., KISHIMOTO-YAMADA K. 2024. Sisyridae and Nevrothidae (Neuroptera) of Japan, with their life history notes. *Japanese Journal of Systematic Entomology* 30: 230–261.
- SHARKEY C.R., FUJIMOTO M.S., LORD N.P., SHIN S., MCKENNA D.D., SUVOROV A., MARTIN G.J., BYBEE S.M. 2017. Overcoming the loss of blue sensitivity through opsin duplication in the largest animal group, beetles. *Scientific Reports* 7: 8.
- SNYMAN L.P., OHL M., PIRK C.W.W., SOLE C.L. 2020. A review of the biology and biogeography of Mantispidae (Neuroptera). *Insect Systematics & Evolution* 52: 125–166.
- SOLE C.L., SCHOLTZ C.H., BALL J.B., MANSELL M.W. 2013. Phylogeny and biogeography of southern African spoon-winged lacewings (Neuroptera: Nemopteridae: Nemopterinae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 66: 360–368.
- SPEAKMAN J.R., RYDELL J., WEBB P.I., HAYES J.P., HAYS G.C., HULBERT I.A.R., MCDEVITT R.M. 2000. Activity patterns of insectivorous bats and birds in northern Scandinavia (69° N), during continuous midsummer daylight. *Oikos* 88: 75–86.
- STEVENS M., RUXTON G.D. 2012. Linking the evolution and form of warning coloration in nature. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 279: 417–426.
- TAUBER C.A., TAUBER M.J., ALBUQUERQUE G.S. 2014. Debris-carrying in larval Chrysopidae: unraveling its evolutionary history. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America* 107: 295–314.
- van der KOOI C.J., STAVENGA D.G., ARIKAWA K., BELUŠIČ G., KELBER, A. 2021. Evolution of insect color vision: from spectral sensitivity to visual ecology. *Annual Review of Entomology* 66: 435–461.
- van ZYL A., van der LINDE T.C.de K., van der WESTHUIZEN M.C. 1996. Ecological aspects of pitbuilding and non-pitbuilding antlions (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae) in the Kalahari. *African Entomology* 4: 143–152.
- VAS J., ÁBRAHÁM L., MARKÓ V. 1999. Study of nocturnal and diurnal activities of lacewings (Neuropteroidea: Raphidioptera, Neuroptera) by suction trap. *Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica* 34: 149–152.
- VAS J., ÁBRAHÁM L., MARKÓ V. 2001. Methodological investigations on a Neuropteroidea community. *Acta Phytopathologica et Entomologica Hungarica* 36: 101–113.
- WICKLER W. 1968. *Mimicry in Plants and Animals* (translated by Martin R.D.). McGraw-Hill, New York: 1–253.
- YACK J.E., KALKO E.K., SURLYKKE A. 2007. Neuroethology of ultrasonic hearing in nocturnal butterflies (Hedyloidea). *Journal of Comparative Physiology A* 193: 577–590.
- YAGER D.D., MAY M.L. 1990. Ultrasound-triggered, flight-gated evasive maneuvers in the praying mantis *Parasphendale agrionina*: II. Tethered flight. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 152: 41–58.
- YAGER D.D., SPANGLER H.G. 1997. Behavioral response to ultrasound by the tiger beetle *Cicindela marutha* Dow combines aerodynamic changes and sound production. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 200: 649–659.
- YU P., IWANAMI T., YAZAKI H., TSUBUKI M., SAITO K., HAYASHI F. 2023. Cost of defensive spraying by larval *Osmylus hyalinatus* (Neuroptera: Osmylidae) for post-larval development. *Journal of Ethology* 41: 129–139.
- ZHANG R., WANG L., Tian S., Liu Y., Jiang Y., Zhou X., Yang D. Liu X, Wang Y. 2025. Inconsistent performance of multi-type genomic data in phylogenomics of neuropteridan insects, with solutions toward conflicting results. *Systematic Entomology* 50: 855–875.
- ZHENG Y., LIU X. 2025. A mysterious treasure originated from Africa: evolutionary history of the endangered spoon-winged lacewings (Neuroptera: Nemopteridae: Nemopterinae) from China. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 203: zlae026.
- ZIMMERMANN D., KLEPAL W., ASPÖCK U. 2009. The first holistic SEM study of Coniopterygidae (Neuroptera) – structural evidence and phylogenetic implications. *European Journal of Entomology* 106: 651–662.

Tab. 1. Daily activity patterns of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. N: number of male (M) and female (F) adults and larvae (L) examined in this study.

Family	Species	N	Adults	Figure 2	N	Larvae	Figure 3
Inocelliidae	<i>Inocellia japonica</i>	1M	Diurnal	1	1L	Unclear	1–2
Sisyridae	<i>Sisyra nikkoana</i> *	3M1F	Unclear	2–5			
Nevrorthidae	<i>Nipponeurorthus punctatus</i> *	2M1F	Nocturnal	6–8			
Osmylidae	<i>Lysmus harmandinus</i>	1F	Nocturnal	9			
Osmylidae	<i>Spilosmylus nipponensis</i>	1M	Nocturnal	10			
Osmylidae	<i>Spilosmylus tuberculatus</i> *	2M2F	Nocturnal	11–14			
Osmylidae	<i>Osmylus decoratus</i>	1M	Nocturnal	15			
Osmylidae	<i>Osmylus hyalinatus</i>	1M2F	Nocturnal	16–18			
Coniopterygidae	<i>Coniopteryx abdominalis</i>	1A	Unclear	19			
Coniopterygidae	<i>Semidalis aleyrodiformis</i>	1A	Unclear	20			
Dilaridae	<i>Dilar japonicus</i>	1F	Nocturnal	21			
Berothidae	<i>Isosclipteron okamotonis</i>	2M1F	Nocturnal	22–24			
Mantispidae	<i>Austroclimaciella quadrituberculata</i>	1F	Diurnal/ Nocturnal	25			
Mantispidae	<i>Mantispilla japonica</i>	1M3F	Diurnal/ Nocturnal	26–29			
Mantispidae	<i>Mantispilla transversa</i>	2M2F	Diurnal/ (Nocturnal)	30–33			
Chrysopidae	<i>Ankylopteryx gracilis</i>	1M	Nocturnal	34			
Chrysopidae	<i>Apochrysa matsumurae</i>	1M3F	Nocturnal	35–38			
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysopa pallens</i> **	1F	Nocturnal	39	2L	Unclear	3–4
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysoperla nipponensis</i> **	2M4F	Nocturnal	40– 45****	1L	Diurnal	5
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysoperla suzukii</i> **				1L	Diurnal	6
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysotropia ciliata</i>	1M	Nocturnal	46			
Chrysopidae	<i>Italochrysa japonica</i>	2F	Nocturnal	47–48			
Chrysopidae	<i>Mallada desjardinsi</i>	2F	Nocturnal	49–50	3L	Diurnal	7–9
Chrysopidae	<i>Nineta itoi</i> **	2M2F	Nocturnal	51–54			
Chrysopidae	<i>Nineta sp.</i> **	1M	Nocturnal	55			
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada astur</i>	2M1F	Nocturnal	56–58	3L	Unclear	10–12
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada cognatellus</i>	1F	Nocturnal	59			
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada formosanus</i>	1M	Nocturnal	60	2L	Diurnal	13–14
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada parabolus</i>	4M1F	Nocturnal	61–65	3L	Diurnal	15–17
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada prasinus</i>	2F	Nocturnal	66–67			
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada ussuriensis</i>	1F	Nocturnal	68			
Chrysopidae	<i>Semachrysa matsumurae</i>	1M	Nocturnal	69			
Hemerobiidae	<i>Hemerobius japonicus</i>	1M1F	Nocturnal	70–71			
Hemerobiidae	<i>Micromus calidus</i>	1M1F	Nocturnal	72–73			

Family	Species	N	Adults	Figure 2	N	Larvae	Figure 3
Hemerobiidae	<i>Micromus timidus</i>	1M3F	Nocturnal	74–77			
Hemerobiidae	<i>Notiobiella subolivacea</i>	2F	Nocturnal	78–79			
Hemerobiidae	<i>Psectra iniqua</i>	2F	Nocturnal	80–81			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Baliga ryukyensis</i> ***	2M	Nocturnal	82–83			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Myrmeleon bore</i> ***	3M2F	Nocturnal	84–88			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Myrmeleon formicarius</i> ***	1M2F	Nocturnal	89–91			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Myrmeleon trigonois</i> ***	1F	Nocturnal	92			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Dendroleon pupillaris</i>				1L	Unclear	18
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Distoleon contubernalis</i>	1F	Nocturnal	93	1L	Unclear	19
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Euroleon sanxianus</i> ***	1M	Nocturnal	94			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Paraglenurus fulvus</i>	1F	Nocturnal	95			
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Paraglenurus okinawensis</i>				1L	Unclear	20
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Synclisis japonica</i>				6L	Unclear	21–26
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Synclisis kawaii</i>				1L	Unclear	27
Ascalaphidae	<i>Ascalohybris subjacens</i>	3M1F	Crepuscular	96–99			
Ascalaphidae	<i>Suhpalaca iriomotensis</i>	1F	Crepuscular	100			
Ascalaphidae	<i>Suphalomitus okinavensis</i>	3M	Crepuscular	101–103			
Ascalaphidae	<i>Libelloides ramburi</i>	2M1F	Diurnal	104–106			

* also see SAITO *et al.* (2024).

** naked larvae in Chrysopidae, but debris-carrying larvae in other Chrysopidae.

*** pit-building antlion larvae. In our actograph, it is impossible to record the movements of larvae with pits.

**** 40: brown overwintering individual. Others: green individuals.

Tab. 2. Number of individuals of each species of Neuroptera unbitten, bitten but uneaten, eaten, or eaten but regurgitated by the lizard. N: total number of individuals examined. The mean time (s) from heading to biting of the lizard is also shown with the range in parentheses..

Family	Species	N	Unbitten	Bitten but uneaten	Eaten	Eaten but regurgitated	Mean time to be bitten (range) in second
Osmylidae	<i>Osmylus hyalinatus</i> *	3	3	0	0	0	Not examined
Mantispidae	<i>Mantispilla japonica</i>	3	0	0	3	0	6.6 (0.8–17)
Mantispidae	<i>Mantispilla transversa</i>	3	0	0	3	0	35.7 (19–57)
Chrysopidae	<i>Apochrysa matsumurae</i>	3	0	0	3	0	4.7 (4–6)
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysopa pallens</i>	1	0	0	1	0	3,1
Chrysopidae	<i>Chrysoperla nipponensis</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0,6
Chrysopidae	<i>Italochrysa japonica</i>	2	0	0	2	0	22.0 (11–33)
Chrysopidae	<i>Pseudomallada cognatellus</i>	2	0	0	2	0	6.5 (3–10)
Myrmeleontidae	<i>Myrmeleon trigonois</i>	2	0	0	2	0	1.3 (0.5–2)
Ascalaphidae	<i>Ascalohybris subjacens</i>	3	0	3	0	0	17.3 (4–34)
Ascalaphidae	<i>Libelloides ramburi</i>	6	0	0	5	1	Not examined

* also see YU *et al.* (2023).

Fig. 1. A–F: Six types (Types A–F) of insect containers used to record insect activities (arrows, fine infrared beam). G: Pen recorder. H–I: Adults of *Italochrysa japonica* (Chrysopidae) and *Mantisquilla transversa* (Mantispidae) drinking the fermented milk soaked in tissue paper, respectively. J: Adult *Mantisquilla transversa* (Mantispidae) eating an adult mayfly. K–L: 3rd-instar larvae of *Pseudomallada formosanus* (MATSUMURA, 1910) and *Chrysopa pallens* eating the aphids, respectively. M: Adult *Mantisquilla japonica* (Mantispidae) eaten by the lizard. N: Adult *Ascalohybris subjacens* (Ascalaphidae). O: Adult *Libelloides ramburi* (Ascalaphidae).

Fig. 2. 1–15: Actograms of individual adults of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. The X-axis is time of day and Y-axis is the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, ... and the final days during the recording period. If the fine beam passing through the insect containers (Types A–F in Fig. 1A–F) is interrupted by the insect, a 1.5-volt battery current flows and is recorded on a chart paper sent out at 10 mm/h (Fig. 1G). Each underbar shows the light period (white) and dark period (black) of 24 h. Triangles indicate the times when the fermented milk (but also living mayflies for Mantispidae) was given (Fig. 1H–J). For information on the feeding time and frequency, see the text.

Fig. 2. 16–29: Continued.

Fig. 2. 30–46: Continued.

Fig. 2. 47–65: Continued.

Fig. 2. 66–81: Continued.

Fig. 2. 82–95: Continued.

Fig. 2. 96–106: Continued.

Fig. 3. 1–17: Actograms of individual larvae of Raphidioptera and Neuroptera. The X-axis is time of day and Y-axis is the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, ... and the final days during the recording period. If the fine beam passing through the insect containers (Types A–F in Fig. 1A–F) is interrupted by the insect, a 1.5-volt battery current flows and is recorded on a chart paper sent out at 10 mm/h (Fig. 1G). Each underbar shows the light period (white) and dark period (black) of 24 h. Triangles indicate the times when the food (aphids for Chrysopidae, crickets, mealworms, or chironomids for Myrmeleontidae) was given (Fig. 1K, L). For information on the feeding time and frequency, see the text.

Fig. 3. 18–27: Continued.

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